

In-World NPCs: Analysing Artificial Intelligence Precision in Virtual Reality Settings

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Research Instrument

1. Research Objective

To measure the accuracy and effectiveness of AI NPCs in VR scenarios through black-box testing, focusing on output and behaviour without examining internal coding or algorithms.

2. Variables Measured

- **Response Accuracy.** How accurately does the NPC respond to user input?
- **Response Time.** How quickly does the NPC respond after receiving input?
- **Behaviour Consistency.** How consistently does the NPC respond to the same input under the same conditions?
- **Response Relevance.** How relevant and appropriate is the NPC's response to the VR scenario context?
- **User Satisfaction.** The level of user satisfaction with the interaction with the NPC.

3. Data Collection Methods

- **Observation.** Observe and record the NPC's responses to user input in the VR scenario.
- **Questionnaire.** Collect feedback from users after interacting with the NPC.
- **System Logs.** Analyzing system logs to obtain response time data and interaction patterns of the NPC.

4. Testing Instruments

A. Observation

1. **Scenario Description.** Describe the VR scenario used.
2. **Input.** Record the type of input the user gives (e.g., voice commands, gestures, etc.).
3. **NPC Response.** Record the NPC's response in detail.

4. **Accuracy Rating.** Rate the accuracy of the NPC's response (1-5, where 1 = very inaccurate, 5 = very accurate).
5. **Response Time.** Measure the NPC's response time from the moment input is given to the response received (in seconds).
6. **Behaviour Consistency.** Record whether the NPC responds consistently when the same input is repeated (Yes/No).

B. User Questionnaire

1. **Response Relevance.** How relevant was the NPC's response to your input? (1-5, where 1 = very irrelevant, 5 = very relevant)
2. **Response Time.** Did you feel the NPC's response time was quick? (1-5, where 1 = very slow, 5 = very quick)
3. **Behaviour Consistency.** Did the NPC respond consistently to the same input? (1-5, where 1 = very inconsistent, 5 = very consistent)
4. **Overall Satisfaction.** How satisfied were you with interacting with the NPC? (1-5, where 1 = very dissatisfied, 5 = very satisfied)
5. **Additional Comments.** Do you have any additional suggestions or comments regarding the interaction with the NPC?

C. System Log Analysis

1. **Event Log.** Record the time and type of each event occurring during the interaction.
2. **Response Time Analysis.** Calculate the average response time from the system logs.
3. **Behaviour Pattern Analysis.** Analyze the NPC's behaviour patterns based on the logs.

5. Research Procedure

1. Preparation

- Prepare the VR scenario and ensure the devices and AI NPC system function correctly.

2. Execution

- Ask users to interact with the NPC in the predetermined VR scenario.
- Record all observation data and system logs.
- After the interaction, ask users to fill out the questionnaire.

3. Data Analysis

- Analyze observation data, questionnaires, and system logs to measure accuracy, response time, behaviour consistency, relevance, and user satisfaction.

4. Reporting

- Compile a report of the research findings based on data analysis.

6. Example Rating Scale

- **1-5 Likert Scale**
 - 1 = Very Dissatisfied/Inaccurate/Irrelevant/Inconsistent
 - 2 = Dissatisfied/Inaccurate/Irrelevant/Inconsistent
 - 3 = Neutral
 - 4 = Satisfied/Accurate/Relevant/Consistent
 - 5 = Very Satisfied/Very Accurate/Very Relevant/Very Consistent

With this instrument, we can gather the necessary data to evaluate the accuracy and effectiveness of AI NPCs in VR scenarios. Be sure to adjust this instrument to fit the specific needs of your research.

1. Purpose and Objectives

The analysis confirmed the importance of evaluating AI accuracy in NPCs within VR scenarios. The research objectives were refined to focus on:

1. Quantitative measurement of AI accuracy in NPC behaviours.
2. User satisfaction and quality of interaction with AI-driven NPCs.
3. Factors influencing AI performance and accuracy in NPCs.

2. Target Audience

The analysis identified key stakeholders, confirming that VR developers, educational institutions, researchers, and VR users are the primary audience for this research. Their needs and expectations were clarified through surveys and interviews.

3. Context and Environment

The research will be conducted in diverse VR environments, including educational simulations, gaming scenarios, and training modules. This variety ensures a comprehensive assessment of AI-driven NPC performance across different contexts.

4. Needs Assessment Findings

1. **Literature Review:** Existing studies highlighted the challenges in achieving high accuracy in AI-driven NPC behaviours. Common issues include limited adaptability, lack of realism, and inconsistent responses.
2. **Surveys and Interviews:** Data from VR users and developers revealed a high demand for more accurate and responsive NPCs. Key challenges include NPCs failing to understand user commands, unnatural behaviour, and limited interaction depth.
3. **Technical Analysis:** Current AI algorithms were found to be limited in their ability to handle complex, dynamic interactions. Improvements in machine learning techniques and real-time processing were identified as critical needs.

5. Data Collection Methods

The analysis phase confirmed the effectiveness of the chosen data collection methods:

1. **Performance Metrics.** Quantitative data will be collected on the accuracy of NPC responses, error rates, and interaction success rates.
2. **User Feedback.** Qualitative data from user surveys and interviews will provide insights into user satisfaction and interaction quality.
3. **Observation.** Direct observation will help identify specific issues in NPC behaviour that quantitative metrics might miss.

6. Key Questions Answered

1. **Accuracy of AI-driven NPCs.** Preliminary data suggest that current AI-driven NPCs perform with varying accuracy, with significant room for improvement in understanding and responding to user inputs.
2. **User Challenges.** Users frequently encounter issues such as NPCs misunderstanding commands, exhibiting repetitive behaviour, and failing to adapt to changing scenarios.
3. **Impact of AI Algorithms.** Different AI algorithms show varying levels of effectiveness, with more advanced machine learning techniques offering better performance but requiring more computational resources.
4. **Areas for Improvement.** Critical areas for improvement include enhancing NPC adaptability, increasing the realism of NPC interactions, and optimizing AI algorithms for better performance in real-time scenarios.

7. Expected Outcomes

- a. **Understand AI Accuracy Levels.** A clear picture of current AI accuracy levels in NPCs will be established.
- b. **Factors Influencing Accuracy.** The research will identify specific factors that impact AI performance, such as algorithm complexity, data quality, and computational power.
- c. **Recommendations for Improvement.** Practical recommendations will be provided to enhance AI algorithms and NPC development practices, focusing on increasing interaction depth and realism.
- d. **Enhance User Experience.** The goal is to improve user satisfaction and interaction quality in VR scenarios involving AI-driven NPCs, making them more realistic and responsive.

8. Stakeholders Confirmed

The analysis phase reaffirmed the importance of involving VR developers, educational institutions, researchers, and users as key stakeholders. Their input and feedback are critical for the success of this research. By conducting this detailed analysis, we have set a solid foundation for the subsequent phases of the ADDIE model. The insights gained will guide the research's design, development, implementation, and evaluation, ensuring that the objectives are met and the results are actionable and relevant to the stakeholders.